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The Forgotten Land and People of Northeast Nigeria: Pre-Colonial Politics and Administration of Bade Polity, 1500-1904

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Abstract

This paper focuses on the pre-colonial politics and administration of the Bade area from 1500 CE. to 1904 CE. It examines the evolution of Bade politics and administration from the founding of Tagali in 1500 CE. to the centralization of administration in 1904 CE. The paper aims to carefully examine the nature of pre-colonial politics and administration in the Bade area with a view to bring to the fore the peculiarities and similarities inherent in the different stages of the evolution and development of Bade political history. The study through the utilisation of information collected from informants via oral interview shows that politics and administration in Bade evolved over time. Another significant finding of the study is that Bade politics was to some extent influenced by the political activities of powerful neighbouring polities like Hadejia Emirate and Kanem-Borno Empire. The paper concludes that politics and administration in pre-colonial Bade was governed by democratic principles which allowed all qualified adults equal rights to participate in the politics and administration of their respective wards.

Introduction

This study examines the pre-colonial politics and administration of Bade polity in the context of the history of Northeast Nigeria. It is a historical analysis of the nature of Bade polity framed by the transformation of its political and administrative system in the pre-colonial period.

The History of Bade could be traced to the sixteenth century when the first wave of Bade migrants (of the Muguram stock) migrated westward from Dadigar and founded Tagali¹. These Bade migrants became known as the Tagali Bade group. Other Bade Migrants soon followed suit, and as a result, organised themselves into semi-autonomous Bade chiefdoms along the rivers *Komadugu*, *Katagum*, and *Hadejia*. The Gidgid

group (first Bade migrants to Gidgid) soon emerged as the dominant Bade group and took over from the Tagali group as the leading Bade group. Subsequently, the political and administrative system of the Bade area was gradually centralized under the Gidgid rulers. A centralized political and administrative system of government was evolved from 1842, although some Bade and Ngizim polities were still independent of the central government at Gorgaram.

Despite its rich historical and cultural heritage, Bade in recent times remains one of the under researched areas in the study of the history of Northeast Nigeria. The result is a wide information vacuum created by inadequate literature on the history of the area. This gap informed the conduct of the study which seeks to resuscitate and re-echo the long neglected history of Bade.

The paper is divided into six major sections and subsections. The sections are clarification of concept, Origin, Migration and Settlement, Evolution of Bade Political System and Administration, Taxation, Law and Order Enforcement Organisation and Institutions, and Conclusion.

Clarification of Concept

The people of the Bade area were a socio-linguistic group reported to have broken away from other groups in the Kanem/Borno area before the rise of the Borno kingdom². Bade is a member of the West branch of Chadic language family, and as such related to Hausa, the dominant language spoken throughout northern Nigeria. The Bade language closest linguistic relatives are Ngizim, spoken to the south, around Potiskum, and Duwai, spoken east of Gashua.

There are three main dialect varieties of the Bade language, namely; Western Bade with the largest number of speakers, and spoken in Amshi, Dagona, Tagali, Madamuwa; southern Bade, spoken in towns like Katama, Katangana, and Gorgaram; and Gashua Bade spoken in Gashua town and villages fanning out around Gashua. There are considerable variations within each of these three dialect varieties, with every village having its distinctive feature³. It could be concluded that the dialect varieties and distinct features in the villages are evidence of diffusion, interaction, and group relations between Bade groups and other groups in the course of migrations and settlements.

The term Bade will also be used to describe a political unit strategically located between the Sokoto Caliphate and Borno kingdom. The administration of Bade polity had not always been centralized. Rather, as the Bade group continued to split into smaller semi-autonomous groups in the course of their migration, so also was the system of

administration decentralized. That trend continued until the rise of Lawan Babuje who started the foundations of a centralised administration in 1825.

Origin, Migration, and Settlements

According to a version of Bade tradition of origin, the various Bade groups trace their origin to the Arabian Peninsula, to the east of the town of Birni Badar, near Yemen, south west of Mecca⁴. Their ancestors dispersed after a quarrel with the prophet Mohammed (S.A.W), and migrated west. The ancestors of Bade passed north of the Lake Chad on to the Komadugu yobe, they sojourned for a while at Dillawa, east of Geidam, and there upon named the place Badar in memory of their native homeland of Birni Badar in the far east of Arabian Peninsula.

They again migrated from Dillawa (Badar), moving westward until they reached Dadigar in Borsari around the fifteenth century. At Dadigar, their leader had four sons through his wife Walu, their names were; Ago, Muza, Amsayiya (Kwolum), and Dodo (Buyum). While the eldest Ago remained where he was in Dadigar to become the founding father of Bade, Muza went north and founded the Tuareg dynasty. Amsagiya (Kwolum) continued west and founded the Ngizim kingdom. Dodo moved south and founded the Ngazar settlement around Potiskum⁵.

The first wave of Bade migrants to migrate from Dadigar and move further west was a group under Dyagana. He went along the north bank of the Komadugu yobe to set up a settlement at Tagali. This happened in the sixteenth century (around 1500 A.D.). Thus, Tagali was the first political and administrative capital of the Bade country. Dyagana subsequently became the first "Dugum" (Leader/Head Chief) of the Bades⁶. Another Bade group the Unduk Marshi settled at Katamma, while the Gidgid were said to have left Dadigar comparatively late, and having stopped over severally, settled at Gidgid about fifteen miles south-east of Gorgaram. Hence, the most important settlements of Bade country by 1904 were; Tagali, Gungwei, Dumari, Katamma, Gangawa, Dala, Gadini, Zabudum, Usur, and Dagona.

It is important to mention that Dadigar occupies an important position in Bade history for a number of reasons. First, it was at Dadigar that Ago, the progenitor of the Bade dynasty was born. Secondly, it was at Dadigar that the four sons of the leader of Badar agreed to separate with each taking his own section of the group with him. Hence, Dadigar was the dispersal point of the various Bade groups.

It should equally be noted that Islam greatly influenced the tradition of origin of the Bades as both versions point to the Arabian Peninsula as the starting point and original home of the Bades. From the analysis of the above traditions of origin of the Bades, it may be concluded that the people of Bade were not aboriginal to the land they occupy to this day, but had migrated into their present location.

Evolution of Bade Political System and Administration

Politics and Administration of Bade Chiefdoms 1500 CE.-1825 CE.

Before the rise to power of the Gidgid group around 1825, the various Bade settlements were divided into chiefdoms. These Bade chiefdoms were independent of one another. Impressed by the leadership prowess of Lawan Babuje, some of the Bade chiefdoms relegated some aspects of their independence by acknowledging the leadership of the Gidgid group led by Lawan Babuje⁷. The Bade chiefdoms remained semi-autonomous until the Bade political system was gradually centralized by the successors of Lawan Babuje who adopted the Mai title for themselves, starting with Mai Aji.

The chiefdoms continued to function as federating units of the Bade central administration with headquarters at Gorgaram. Mai Saleh reorganised the Bade political system by creating eleven Units out of the former Bade chiefdoms, and appointed Lawans (Unit heads) to oversee the administration of the Units, while the chiefs (now Bulamas or village Heads) were to henceforth function as Wakils of the Lawans. The Unit Heads themselves remained in Gorgaram while their Wakils took charge of tax work⁸.

Administration of Bade From 1825 to 1842

The Gidgid Bade migrants were late in leaving Dadigar. They first settled at Gazair but were driven out by the Fulani. Subsequently, they returned through Dalaturi to Goyin which was situated north of Tagali. The ruler of Tagali at the time, Mada Zabuwa allowed them to stay in Tagali territory around 1780 CE.-1790 CE. The Gidgid stay in Tagali was short-lived as disagreements with the Tagali rulers over leadership forced them to move to Gidgid, about fifteen miles south east of Gorgaram. Their Head chief Dugum Akuya was killed in Gidgid by the Fulani of Hadejia under Sambo Digimsa. Following constant raid by the Fulani, the Gidgid group led by Babuje, Dugum Akuya's son and successor moved to Ayama Kasha, then to Sagma, and Satako.

According to Aji S. Suleiman, Dugum Bugia was the first Head chief of the Gidgid group. He led the Gidgid group to migrate from Dadigar, but was not able to establish a permanent settlement for the Gidgid

group. Like many other Bade chiefs, he obtained the Dugum title from the Mai of Borno around 1759 CE. and reigned for about twenty years 1759 CE-1779 CE. Recorded information about the life of Dugum Bugia is sketchy. Dugum Bugia was succeeded by his son Akuya.

Dugum Akuya appears to be the first documented Head chief of the Gidgid, with available information about his life and circumstance leading to his death. Dugum Akuya founded a permanent settlement for the Gidgid group at Gidgid some fifteen miles south east of Gorgaram. He may thus be referred to as one of the founding fathers of the Gidgid dynasty. He established the Gidgid chiefdom which he reigned over for about twenty five years (1779 CE.-1804 CE.). Dugum Akuya was killed by the Hadejia Fulani under Sarki Sambo⁹. He was succeeded by his son Babuje around 1804 CE.

After Babuje succeeded his father Dugum Akuya as the leader of the Gidgid group, he was rewarded with the title of '*Lawan*' by Shehu Lamido of Borno for supporting Borno forces in its defeat of Wari. But continuous interference in the domestic affairs of Bade chiefdoms, demand for slaves, and constant raids by the Fulani, especially, the Hadejia Fulani compelled Lawan Babuje to solicit the corporation of other Bade chiefs to unanimously resist the interference and demands of both Borno and the Hadejia Fulani. This move led to the formation of a pan-Bade confederacy, a social, economic and political alliance of the various Bade chiefdoms against external threats to their collective sovereignty and independence¹⁰.

With the corporation of Tagali, Katamma, Dumari, and Gungwei, the fortified town of Gorgaram was built under the supervision of Lawan Babuje in 1825 CE. Gradually, the various Bade Chiefdoms came to acknowledge the leadership of Lawan Babuje. The Bade alliance was so formidable that neither Hadejia nor Borno could break the independence of Bade. Sadly, Tagali was attacked and sacked by Shehu Umar of Borno, the consequence of the refusal of its rulers to acknowledge the leadership of Lawan Babuje¹¹. Gorgaram thus replaced Tagali as the administrative headquarters of the Bade country.

Lawan Babuje died in 1842 CE. and was succeeded by his son Aji who adopted the '*Mai*' title, perhaps to assert and straighten his authority over the various Bade groups, signify the independence of Bade, and equate the Mai Bade with Borno. However, the Mai Bade was still being referred to as '*Ajia*' (District Head) by the Kanuri of Borno. The Kanuri still thought of Bade as a District of the Borno Empire. More so, it was not all the Bade and Ngizim polities that were brought under the control of Gorgaram. There are conflicting reports about Lawan Babuje's death. A.S. Suleiman reports that Lawan Babuje was de-

throned by his son Maina Aji after he became blind, and died in 1845 CE. But information from other sources maintained that Lawan Babuje died seven years after the death of Shehu Lamido in 1835 CE.

Administration of Bade From 1842 to 1904

Although the process to centralize the administration of Bade had started under Lawan Babuje, it was completed and consolidated by his descendants who adopted the title '*Mai*' an equivalent of a Ruler. The probable reason for adopting the *Mai* title by the descendants of Lawan Babuje was to signify the independence of Bade, as well as show that the ruler of Bade was of equal status with the Mai of Borno¹². This could also be attributed to the political decline of the Borno Empire at the time.

However, the Mai Bade was still being referred to as '*Ajia*' (District Head) by the Kanuri of Borno. The Kanuri still thought of Bade as a District of the Borno Empire. More so, there were some Bade and Ngizim wards that were not directly administered and politically controlled by the central administration at Gorgaram.

Mai Aji Lawan Babuje's successor was a warrior who not only defended the sovereignty of Bade, but also carried out raids into Borno territories. He died in 1893 CE. after about fifty years of successful reign and peace. He was succeeded by his son Maina Duma. Four years into Mai Duma's reign, Rabeh's forces under Shehu Dab sacked Gorgaram and caused Maina Saleh the younger brother of the deposed Mai Duma to be summoned from Allagueno where he was living. On ascending the Bade throne, Mai Saleh embarked on intensive political and administrative re-organisation of Bade political system. He divided Bade into units and straightened the central administrative machinery in Gorgaram.

The *Mai* was at the helm of administration at Gorgaram the administrative capital of Bade country. The *Makinta* was the chief minister and administrator of Gorgaram. He was one of the *Mai*'s most trusted officials and was in charge of the administration of the capital in the *Mai*'s absence¹³. At the formation periods, the Head chiefs of the various chiefdoms retained some measure of autonomy; they continued sending tribute and men to Gorgaram as the need arose. However, following the success of Lawan Babuje and his successors in curtailing the interference of Hadejia and Borno in Bade domestic affairs, these chiefs gradually relinquished their powers to the *Mai* at Gorgaram, who in turn centralized the administration.

There were few exceptions where some Head chiefs and their subjects refused to acknowledge the leadership of the *Mai*. In such instances, Gorgaram either withdrew its support for such chiefdom which rendered it vulnerable to attacks, as was the case with Tagali, or the *Mai* could decide to march against the rebellious unit taking hostage of its leaders or their relatives as a guarantee for the good behaviour of the area, as was the case in Allagueno where the keeper of the shrine was taken hostage by Mai Saleh. In Katamma the Unit head was briefly detained in Gorgaram for failing to contain a disturbance in the area.

Taxation

There are no written records on the taxation system in Bade polities before 1825 CE. However, information obtained from oral informants seems to suggest that there were many ways of generating revenue to finance the administrative machinery. These informants however did not provide clear details of the rates and percentage in their narratives. The gaps in such oral narratives may have led the British colonial administrators to conclude that there were no systematic methods of taxation throughout Borno and Bade by extension, prior to the arrival of the British.

Prior to the rise to prominence of Lawan Babuje and the subsequent unification of the various Bade polities in 1825 CE, Bade polities (chiefdoms) operated independently as regard revenue generation. Hence, the method of generating revenue differed slightly from one Bade polity to the other. The bulk of the revenue was derived from levy imposed on nomadic cattle owners and gifts, especially from immigrants from Katagum, Hadejia, and Borno who used the rivers for fishing¹⁴. There were also practices in certain Bade settlements and villages like Gashua, Jawa, Jawa-Kura, Tarabutu, and so on, where a man of great wealth agrees to pay for his entire village over a period of time, usually a year, to obtain certain titles.

The payment was usually in the form of farm produce or livestock, depending on the occupation or source of wealth of the person involved. It was also reported that apart from valour, military strategy and administrative prowess, wealth was also a contributory factor to the Gidgid Bade migrant group accepting Dugum Akuya as their chief¹⁵. As for levy on grazing lands, it was paid in the form of livestock and dairy produce like cows, goats, sheep, milk, and cheese. The immigrant fisher men gave certain proportion of their catch to the host village through its chief¹⁶.

Taxation in Bade From 1825 CE.-1904 CE.

From 1825 CE, Bade political administrative system gradually evolved from a system of mutually independent chiefdoms to a centralized administration with headquarters at Gorgaram. The office of the *Mai* Bade (Ruler of Bade country) was created, and Bade revenue system remained unchanged except for the introduction of annual tributes and incorporation of the *Sadaka* and *Binimram* from Borno. The '*Sadaka*' was a levy imposed on grain, while the '*Haku-Birnimram*' was a kind of tax imposed on all villages based on individual wealth.

The *Sadaka* and *Haku-Birnimram* constituted significant portion of the annual tributes sent to Gorgaram. The Shuwa Arabs and Fulani nomadic cattle owners continued to pay their taxes in form of a fairly levied grazing fee. The village Heads apportioned the taxes, which they collected and remitted same to Gorgaram as tribute. However, the practice of tax evasion and leakages could not be completely ruled out in the pre-colonial Bade taxation system.

Law and Order Enforcement Organisations and Institutions

The Army

Before 1842, prior to the rise of Lawan Babuje, Bade chiefdoms did not have a standing army, but a volunteer corps made up of mostly renowned hunters. The Head chief was usually the commander-in-chief of the volunteer corps, which was usually placed under the command of the *Kachallan* (Head hunter). The volunteer corps was usually assembled in times of war, and disbanded as soon as the war was over and stability restored.

The Mai's Royal Guards

From 1825, consequent upon the establishment of the pan-Bade confederacy, the various Bade chiefdoms began to send some of their warrior hunters to Gorgaram, at the request of Lawan Babuje. These ex-members of the defunct volunteer corps were subsequently trained and organised into a standing army based at Gorgaram. Based on the new arrangement, the *Mai* Bade assumed the position of the commander-in-chief of the Bade army, while a trusted official was entrusted with the responsibility of managing the affairs of the army on behalf of the *Mai* Bade.

The Judiciary

The Chief's Court

Prior to 1804, the various Bade chiefdoms operated a judicial system that could best be referred to as the chief's Court System. Under this

arrangement, the Head chief (*Lawan/Bulama* used in the western Bade areas, while *Dugum* was used in the eastern Bade areas) presided over court hearings. He was assisted by a jury panel. Members of the jury panel included the *Wakili*, the *Kachalla*, the *Maganan*, ward heads, and so on. The court convened at the instance of the Head chief through the *wakili*. In the absence of the Head chief, the *wakili* presided over the court. The jurisdiction of the court was limited to the domains under the control of the Head chief. Cases related to land disputes, tax, murder, theft, adultery, among others were brought before the chief's court for hearing.

Lawan Babuje's Court

From 1804, the Bades of the Gidgid Chifdom began to rise to prominence under the leadership of its Head chief, Lawan Babuje. Thus, by 1825, Lawan Babuje began a process of gradual restructuring of the administrative machinery. The gradual centralisation of the Bade political and administrative system was made possible by the founding of the fortified town of Gorgaram. Lawan Babuje presided over the court based at Gorgaram. He was assisted by a jury panel comprised of selected head chief's.

The court sessions were irregular as most of the head chiefs could not travel to Gorgaram due to poor health and flooded condition of the roads, especially during the rainy season. The jurisdiction of the court was limited to the domains of the chiefs that recognized the leadership of Lawan Babuje. This excluded Tagali and some Bade and Ngizim chiefdoms that refused to acknowledge the supremacy of the Gidgid. Most cases handled by the court bordered on boundary land disputes, tax and annual tributes, sabotage, among other aggregate cases. Minor cases were still being handled by the various chief's courts.

The Mai's Court

The *Mai's* court replaced Lawan Babuje's court. In 1842, Aji succeeded his father, Lawan Babuje. He was the first Bade leader to adopt the *Mai* title and continued the centralization of Bade political and administrative system began by Lawan Babuje. He expanded the territorial frontiers of Bade and restructured the judiciary. Due to the expansion of Bade political frontiers, more official titles were borrowed from the neighbouring Kanuri, Hausa, and Fulani polities. Some of these official titles were modified to suit Bade needs.

As a result more officials were appointed to the Jury panel of the *Mai's* court. Some of the newly appointed members of the *Mai's* court included the *Waziri*, *Talba*, *Kaigama*, *Galadima*, *Makinta*, among others.

The *Mai* presided over court hearing, and the jurisdiction of the court covered all the area under the domain of the *Mai*. Most members of the jury resided at Gorgaram. The court handled all cases irrespective of their gravity.

The Prison

Documented information on the history of the Bade prison system is quite scanty. This is in the light of the fact that we have not been able to retrieve any documented source material on the origin of the Bade prison system, especially during the pre-Gorgaram Era (1500 CE.-1824 CE.) and the Gorgaram Era (1825 CE.-1903 CE.). Therefore, we have been compelled to rely on oral information in the attempt to reconstruction of the history of the prison system in pre-Gorgaram and Gorgaram Bade. Sadly, oral information regarding the Origin of the prison system in Bade is not specific and detailed, but rather is a general overview of the transformation process of the prison system in Bade.

Prison System in Pre-Gorgaram Bade 1500 CE.-1824 CE.

The prison in pre-Gorgaram Bade the prison was located in the court of the Head chief of a particular Bade chiefdom. It was a section of the royal court where erring officials, runaway and recaptured slaves, and accused persons awaiting trials were detained, pending the outcome of investigation and hearing of their cases by the chiefs Court. A custodian or caretaker was appointed usually from among the chief's senior guards to secure the detainees. He was often assisted by other members of the chief's royal guards.

How long an accused was kept in custody was determined by the gravity of the crime he has been accused of, the outcome of investigation, and conveyance of the Chiefs jury presided over by the Head Chief. After an investigation has been concluded and the jury conveyed, an accused was set free without further delay if he was found innocent of the crimes he was accused to have committed. If on the other hand an accused person was convicted, the penalty was either to be fined, banished or sentenced to dead depending on the gravity of the offence.

Normally offenders accused and convicted of thievery were fined and/or banished depending on the customs of the Bade polity involved. Adulterers and fornicators were often banished, while murderers were sentenced to death, according to the customs and traditions of some Bade Groups. The nature of punishment meted out depended on the customs and traditions of the Bade polity involved. The Caretakers

and/or Custodians work was done as soon as judgement was passed, and the accused person acquitted or convicted¹⁷. It may be safely concluded that the prison system in pre-Gorgaram Bade societies had not fully evolved.

Prison System in Gorgaram Bade 1825 CE.-1903 CE.

With the construction of the fortified town of Gorgaram and its ascension as the headquarters of Bade country, the prison system began to undergo a gradual transformation process. This was chiefly as a result of the centralization of the Bade political administration which began during the reign of Lawan Babuje. The process was completed during the reign of Mai Aji (1842 CE.-1893 CE.). Within this period, the *Mai's* palace at Gorgaram had been completed and there also arose the need to contain erring and obstinate District chiefs (formerly Head chiefs of Bade chiefdoms). As a result, a section of the *Mai's* palace at Gorgaram was set aside to house such erring chiefs or their relatives held in custody at Gorgaram to guarantee the good behaviour of their domains¹⁸.

A separate building was also constructed outside the *Mai's* palace to also house other persons accused of various crimes and awaiting trials. A trusted official was appointed by the *Mai* to ensure the safety and well being, especially of the erring or stubborn chiefs and their relatives. The chief of the prison was appointed on a permanent basis, and granted the right to recruit members of the royal prison guards. Thus, the prison system during the Gorgaram era was gradually organised and institutionalized.

Conclusion

From the foregoing analysis, it is obvious that the administration of the Bade polity had been centralized by internal forces. The paper showed that past leaders of various Bade groups had obtained their political titles from Bornu. For example, Dyagana of Tagali obtained the 'Dugum' from the *Mai* of Bornu, and Babuje of Gidgid obtained the '*Lawan*' title from the Shehu of Bornu, to mention but a few. It was also pointed out that Babuje's successors adopted the '*Mai*' title as a way to assert their authority over the whole of Bade as well as signify their independence from Hadejia and Bornu.

Political power and authority was decentralized through a democratic process of electing the Head chief rather than inheritance through hereditary, although there were few exceptions when the position of the Head chief was hereditary. Furthermore, prior to the centralization of administration, Bade Head Chiefs remained in power for only

as long as it pleased their subjects. Also, the title associated with the Head chief varied among Bade chiefdom; hence, there was the *Dugum*, *Lawan*, *Mada*, *Bulama*, *Bela*, and so on. The Head chief was responsible for the general administration of his domain. Apart from defence and administration of justice, tax collection was an important responsibility of the Head chief. This function was in most cases delegated to other administrative officials, mostly ward heads.

Endnotes

- 1 Ali Ibrahim. (22nd August, 2017). Interviewed at Tagali.
- 2 Akilahyel Ali Sunama. (3th November, 2016). Interviewed at Gashua
- 3 Schuh, Russell G. (2001), *The Chadic Languages of Yobe State*. Los Angeles: University of California
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- 5 Aji Saleh Suleiman, (4th November, 2016) Interviewed at Gashua
- 6 Ali Ibrahim (22nd August, 2017) Interviewed at Tagali
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- 8 Yakubu S. Aminu (22nd August, 2017) Interviewed at Tagali
- 9 Aji Saleh Suleiman (4th November, 2016) Interviewed at Gashua
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- 13 Alhaji Isa Ahmed, (11th June, 2017) Interviewed at Gashua
- 14 Baba Musa Babuje. (18th August, 2017) Interviewed at Gorgaram
- 15 Aji Saleh Suleiman. (4th November, 2016) Interviewed at Gashua
- 16 Isa Rabi. (18th August, 2017). Interviewed at Gorgaram
- 17 Alhaji Ali Ibrahim. (22nd August, 2017). Interviewed at Tagali
- 18 Ibrahim Hamid. (24th January, 2018). Interviewed at Gashua

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